

Ionisation Potentials and Grating Energies of Atoms in the Solid State.

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According to Bohr's theory, an electron revolving about its stable orbit is acted on towards the centric positive charge with a Coulombian force of attraction. The energy of such an electron orbit can be calculated as the sum of the potential energy and the kinetic energy of rotation of the electron. For a circular orbit it can be shown that the average kinetic energy of the electron in the atom is just one-half as great as the average potential energy, but the two act in opposite senses. This may mean that the sum total of energies of an orbit is potential in character, which gradually diminishes away from the centre to the limit of the field of force. The work done when an electron falls from infinity to the normal orbit is called the ionisation work, which will be a measure of the energy of the normal level of the atom. In the intermediate space also, there are a number of stationary orbits having, in suspension of the principles of electro-magnetic radiations, the peculiar "quantum condition" of the orbits which are radiation-less inspite of the revolution of the electrons in those orbits. In this sense, possibly, Langmuir (*Science*, 1921, 53, 290) suggested that if in Bohr's theory a repulsive quantum force varying inversely as the cube of the distance is assumed, in addition to the Coulombian force of attraction, kinetic energy in Bohr's equation of orbital motion can be really substituted by a form of potential energy and the system reduces to a truly static one.

In crystalline solid bodies where arrangements of atoms are presumably static, such a law of force composed of an electrostatic force of attraction with a repulsive force following the inverse power law, *i.e.*, B/r^{n+1} (r representing the distance between the atoms) has been assumed by Born.* According to Madelung's (*Phys. Zeit.*, 1918, 19, 524) calculation, the resultant potential energy under such

* Born—*Verh. d. D. Phys. Ges.*, (1918-1921); "Atom Theorie des Festen Zustandes," 1922.

a system of forces, in an electrical system of alternately positive and negative charges can be expressed as

$$W_{\text{pot}} = -\frac{A}{\delta} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right) \dots\dots\dots (1) \text{ where } A \text{ is Madelung}$$

constant, dependent on the lattice type and δ the distance between the ions.

Relationship between Compressibility and Grating Energy.

If V represents the change in volume produced by the external pressure P , the total energy $W = W_{\text{pot}} + p.dV$.

The equilibrium condition requires that

$$\frac{dW_{\text{pot}}}{d\delta} + p \cdot \frac{dV}{d\delta} = 0 \text{ whence } p = -\frac{1}{3\delta^2} \cdot \frac{dW_{\text{pot}}}{d\delta}$$

By definition, compressibility of the crystal, β , is given by

$$\beta = -\frac{1}{V} \cdot \left(\frac{dV}{dp}\right)_{T=0} = \frac{9\delta}{d^2W_{\text{pot}}/d\delta^2} = \frac{9\delta^4}{A(n-1)},$$

$$\text{or } \beta^{\frac{1}{4}} = \sqrt[4]{\frac{9}{A(n-1)}} \cdot \delta \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Combining (1) and (2)

$$\beta^{\frac{1}{4}} \cdot W_{\text{pot}} = \frac{A(n-1)^{\frac{3}{4}} \cdot 9^{\frac{1}{4}}}{n}$$

i.e., the product of the lattice energy and the fourth root of the compressibility of the elements will be a constant quantity depending on the lattice type and the unknown exponent of the repulsive force.

In the following table, the compressibilities of elements in the solid state will be compared to their potential energies in the gaseous state, *i.e.*, to their ionisation energies. From the constancies of the products, it appears that the compressibilities of elements in the solid state will be proportional to their values in the gaseous state and similarly the grating energies of the elements in the solid state will be proportional to their ionisation energies in the gaseous state. This latter view seems to be justified also by Eve's (*Nature*, 1921, 107, 552) results in which the products of ionisation potentials and Bragg's diameters of combining atoms remain constant for the same group of atoms,

TABLE I.*

	1	2	3	4	5	
Mendeleef's groups.	Elements.	Structure.	I. P. (volts).	Compressibility $\beta \times 10^{12}$ †	$\beta^{\frac{1}{2}} \times 10^6$.	I. P. $\times \beta^{\frac{1}{2}}$.
I A.	Li	B. C. C.	5.368	9.6	1.732	9.29
	Na	„	5.11	15.4	1.98	10.12
	K	„	4.32	31.5	2.37	10.23
	Rb	?	4.158	40.0	2.52	10.46
	Cs	?	3.877	61.0	2.76	10.82
I B.	Cu	F. C. C.	7.80	0.75	0.93	7.25
	Ag	„	7.64	0.84	0.95	7.27
	Au	„	9.125	0.47	0.81	7.39
II A.	Mg	H. C. P.	7.613	2.90	1.313	9.9
	Ca	F. C. C.	6.09	5.07	1.55	9.4
	Sr	„	5.67	(10.6) (comp.)	—	10.2
	Ba	„	5.19	(14.7) (comp.)	—	10.2
II B.	Zn	H. C. P.	9.353	1.5	1.11	10.36
	Cd	„	8.955	1.9	1.174	10.61
	Hg(solid)	„	10.39	1.13 (comp.)	—	10.7
III A.	Al	F. C. C.	5.96	1.33	1.07	6.40
III B.	Tl	F. C. C.	7.30	2.60	1.27	9.27
IV A.	C(dia- mond).	F. C. C.	11.20	1.16 ††	0.631	7.25
IV B.	Pb	„	7.93	2.33	1.235	9.79
VII A.	Mn	„	7.36	0.84	0.95	6.99
VIII.	Fe	„	8.20**	0.4	0.79	6.48
	Ni	„	9.90**	0.27	0.72	7.13

* Ionisation values are mostly taken from Franck-Jordan's "Anregung Von Quanten Sprungen," 1926.

**Provisionally for Fe (Laporte, *Zeit. Physik*, 26, 18) and for Ni (Bechert and Sommer, *Ann. der Physik*, 77, 359) are taken.

† Kaye and Laby, "Table of Constants", pp. 28, 29 (see compressibilities.)

†† Adams, *Washington Academy of Science*, 1921, 11, 45.

Apparently in Table I (col. 5), two constants are found for two series of elements. Elements of Group IB have the same valency as the elements of Group IA and as regards their crystalline structure they represent elements of Group IIA. But it is interesting to find that the constants of Group IB differ from either of Group IA or Group IIA (Table I, col. 5). This clearly points out that the change in two series is mainly determined by the order of compression, a substance may undergo, or according as the exponential coefficient n is large or small (*vide* Haber's results, Table I, row 1). From the constancy of the products in the case of elements of Group II A & B the compressibility of Hg (solid) and those of Sr and Ba have been provisionally computed. The result for Al seems to be peculiar.

Metal Crystals.

Incidentally it has been assumed in the foregoing considerations that electrons inside a metal are arranged in space-lattices to form crystalline solids. Haber (*Sitzungsber.*, 1919, 506, 990), on the assumption that in monovalent metal crystals structures are of haloid types in which only the negative ion has been replaced by an electron, determined the exponent of repulsive coefficient n from compressibility data and thence computed their grating energies (Table II, row 2). It was also shown that by vaporisation of metallic crystals, isolated atoms could be produced which were capable of subsequent ionisation.

$$[M] = (M) - D \dots \dots \dots (\text{sublimation})^*$$

$$(M) = (M^+) + e - J \dots \dots \dots (\text{ionisation})$$

$$[M] = (M^+) + e - (D + J) \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

or the lattice energy $V_m = D + J$. Both these quantities are experimentally known and their calculated V_m is entered in Table II (row IV).

It may be seen (Table II, row 1) that Haber's n lies between 2.4 and 3.6 for alkali metals and between 8.0 and 9.0 for Cu, Ag, etc. This explains why different constants appear in Table I (col. 5) for the two series of metals. Exactly in the same way, on the assumption

* Here and in the following equations parenthesis () refers to gaseous state and brackets [] to solid state.

of cubic structures for alkali metals, and on the assumption of a law of force $F = E \cdot e / \delta^2 (1 - \frac{c}{\delta})$ where $c = 1.75$, a distance at which the force changes from one of attraction to repulsion. Sir J. J. Thomson ("The Electron in Chemistry," p. 120) has calculated the compressibilities which are well within the range of experimental results. Calculated grating energies using J. J. Thomson's equation $V_m = -1.825 e^2 / \delta$, computed by taking for δ the experimentally determined lattice distances * in A. U. (e.g., Li, 3.50; Na, 4.30; K, 5.20) are given in Table II, row 3. Values for alkali metals as computed by J. J. Thomson, (*loc. cit.*, p. 121) determining δ from the cube root of molecular volumes seem to be too high.

TABLE II. **

	Li.	Na.	K.	Rb.	Cs.	Cu.	Ag.
I. Computed n from compressibility (Haber).	2.44	2.9	3.18	3.64	3.62	8.0	9.0
II. Computed grating energy V_m (volt) (Haber).	6.51	5.69	5.04	5.04	4.68	11.73	10.5
III. Computed grating energy V_m (volt) (J. J. Thomson).	7.47	6.08	5.03	—	—	—	—
IV. $V_m = (J + D)$ (volts) (experimental).	7.09	6.25	5.12	4.98	4.66	10.69	10.17
V. $V_m = \phi_e + \phi_{M^+}$ (volts) (experimental).	7.13	6.29	5.09	4.73	4.65	—	—

As metal crystals are supposed to be composed of electrons and positive residues as ions, the lattice energy can also be calculated from the work of dissociation of the crystal ions into gaseous ions. This can be shown as follows:—

$$[M] = [M^+] + e - \phi_e \dots \dots \dots (A) \text{ (evaporation of negative electrons).}$$

$$[M^+] = (M^+) - \phi_{M^+} \dots \dots \dots (B) \text{ (evaporation of positive ion).}$$

* A. H. Compton, "X-Rays and Electrons," p. 116.

** Table II, rows (I, II and IV) are taken from *Handbuch der Physik*, Vol. 22, p. 437.

Adding together

$$[M] = (M^+) + e - (\phi_e + \phi_{M^+})$$

or
$$V_m = \phi_e + \phi_{M^+} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Both these quantities—energy of expulsion of electrons from solid metals (A) and that of evaporation of positive ions (B)—can variously be calculated.

Energy of expulsion of electrons from metals (Eqn. A) can be determined mainly from (a) the thermionic work function in Richardson's equation for electron emission where the thermionic current flowing per unit area per sec,

$$i = A \cdot T^2 \cdot e^{-\phi_e/kT}$$

where A is a universal constant, k the gas constant and T the absolute temperature. It can be shown that ϕ_e in volts is related to Richardson's b by $\phi_e = 8.62 \times 10^{-5} \times b$, or from (b) photo-electric threshold frequency such that $e \cdot \phi_e = h\nu_0$, ν_0 being the threshold frequency and h Planck's constant. It may be pointed that for alkali metals, the threshold frequency is not so definitely known, hence they are calculated from an approximate relation $\frac{3}{2}\nu_0 = \nu_{max}$; ν_{max} stands for selective photo-electric effect according to Richardson's* theory of photo-electron emission.

ϕ_e expressed in volts as determined by either of the methods are given below:—

	Li.	Na.	K.	Rb.	Cs.
Volts.....	2.85	1.182 } 2.100 }	1.55	1.45	1.36

For the determination of the energy of evaporation of positive ions, the concept of Born and Fajans (*Ber. Deut. Phys. Ges.*, 1918, 20, 712) regarding the heat of hydration of gaseous ions is of much practical use. Heat of hydration has been defined as the difference between the heat necessary for the dissociation of crystal ions into free gaseous ions and the 'heat of solution' of these ions in water. From a consideration of the electro-static energies of ions in vacuum and water, it can be shown that the electro-static energy of the gaseous ions will be ($K=81$) times greater than in solution or what means the

* Richardson, "Emission of Electricity from Hot Bodies," 1921, p. 41.
Allen, "Photo-electricity," 1925, p. 163.

same thing that the heat of hydration of gaseous ions will be for all practical purposes identical to the heat of evaporation of positive ions.

Following a mode of calculation by Fajans, based on thermochemistry, the following method for the determination of the heat of hydration of gas ions has been worked out which is independent of the lattice energy concept.

According to Witmer (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Amer.*, 1926, 12, 23c) heat of dissociation for H₂ molecules (100,100 cal.)—

$$\frac{1}{2}(\text{H}_2) = (\text{H}) - 50,050 \text{ cal} \dots\dots (\text{dissociation of the molecule})$$

$$(\text{H}) = (\text{H}^+) + e - 312,000 \text{ cal} \dots\dots (\text{ionisation of the atom})$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(\text{H}_2) = (\text{H}^+) + e - 362,050 \text{ cal} \dots\dots\dots (\text{C}).$$

Taking potassium as representative of any metal M, it can be shown that

$$[\text{K}] = (\text{K}) - 21,000 \text{ cal.}$$

$$(\text{K}) = (\text{K}^+) + e - 99,000 \text{ cal.}$$

The result of Eqn. (3); $[\text{K}] = (\text{K}^+) + e - 120,000 \text{ cal} \dots\dots\dots (\text{D})$

$$[\text{K}] + \text{aq} = \text{K}^+_{\text{aq}} + \text{OH}^-_{\text{aq}} + \frac{1}{2}(\text{H}_2) + 48,100 \text{ cal. (chemical action.)}$$

$$\text{H}^+_{\text{aq}} + \text{OH}^-_{\text{aq}} = \text{aq} \text{ (heat of formation)}$$

$$[\text{K}] + \text{H}^+_{\text{aq}} = \text{K}^+_{\text{aq}} + \frac{1}{2}(\text{H}_2) + 61,700 \text{ cal.} \quad (\text{E})$$

Substituting Eqns. (C) and (D) in Eqn. (E),

$$(\text{K}^+) + \text{H}^+_{\text{aq}} = \text{K}^+_{\text{aq}} + (\text{H}^+) - 180,350 \text{ cal.}$$

$$\text{or } (\text{H}^+) - \text{H}^+_{\text{aq}} - (\text{K}^+) - \text{K}^+_{\text{aq}} = 180,350 \text{ cal.}$$

In other words, $W_{\text{H}^+} - W_{\text{K}^+} = 180,350 \text{ cal.}$, where W stands for heat of hydration of gas ions. This gives the heat of hydration as the difference in W for two anions. After checking these results with the heats of hydrations of individual gas ions determined experimentally from a knowledge of the absolute electrode potentials by Born (*Zeit. Physik*, 1920, 1, 45) heats of hydrations of gaseous ions are expressed in equivalent volts by the expression,

$$\frac{W \times 300 \times 4.7 \times 10^7}{eN} = V \text{ (volts),}$$

e being the electronic charge (E.S.U), N the number of molecules per gram molecule.

Energy of Evaporation of Positive Ions.

	Li.	Na.	K.	Rb.	Cs.
Volts.....	4.78	4.47	3.54	3.28	3.29.

Grating energy as calculated from the energy of sublimation of ions is entered in Table II, row V. The agreement between the results in rows IV and V clearly indicates that the process of ionisation of an individual gas atom is the same as that of the assemblage of ions in crystal lattices. Electron affinities in the two cases, however, must differ. In the cases of crystal ions, as more than one ion are packed together due to the mutual influence of neighbouring ions, the force of attraction is considerably reduced.

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